

Towards Brain State Classification with Functional Ultrasound Imaging

B. Gambosi¹, C. Buda¹, N. Toschi^{2,3,4,*} and L. Astolfi^{1,*}

¹ *Department of Computer Control and Management Engineering, University of Rome La Sapienza (IT)*

² *Department of Biomedicine and Prevention, University of Rome Tor Vergata (IT)*

³ *A.A. Martinos Center for Biomedical Imaging, Harvard Medical School (USA)*

⁴ *Department of Psychology, School of Biological Sciences, University of Cambridge (UK)*

*These authors equally contributed to this work.

Correspondence to: benedetta.gambosi@uniroma1.it

Abstract—This study investigates the potential of functional ultrasound imaging (fUSI) as a promising, non-invasive, and cost-effective tool for identifying brain states and detecting pathological changes. We simulated brain activity using a Wilson-Cowan mass model, converting electrophysiological signals into fUSI data through a hemodynamic response function (HRF). By introducing pathological alterations to the model, we assessed fUSI’s ability to distinguish between healthy (control) and diseased (Alzheimer’s disease, epilepsy) conditions using a neural network classifier. Based on 100 realizations per condition, classification on simulated fUSI signals remained high for Alzheimer’s disease (80% accuracy vs. 95% on electrophysiology), but was lower for epilepsy (65% vs. 95%), likely due to the fast, transient nature of epileptic activity. Nonetheless, our findings show that fUSI can reliably detect distinct brain states in most cases, offering exciting prospects for its use in real-time neurological assessments.

Keywords—Functional Ultrasound Imaging, Neuronal Mass Model, Epilepsy, Alzheimer’s Disease

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to identify and classify distinct brain states in a simple, cost-effective manner represents a key objective in computational neuroscience and clinical diagnostics. Existing neuroimaging techniques like functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and electroencephalography (EEG) each provide valuable insights into brain activity. However, fMRI is expensive and often inaccessible due to its infrastructural requirements, while EEG, despite its excellent temporal resolution, offers limited spatial specificity [1].

Emerging ultrasound-based approaches aim to address some of these limitations by providing a non-invasive, relatively affordable, and potentially high-resolution method to investigate brain function [2], [3], [4]. In particular, functional ultrasound imaging (fUSI) exploits neurovascular coupling, a principle whereby neural activation triggers localized changes in blood flow and volume, thereby producing an ultrasound-visible hemodynamic response [5]. Unlike traditional Doppler ultrasound, fUSI focuses on ultra-sensitive measurements of cerebral blood volume (CBV) and cerebral blood flow (CBF), allowing for the detection of subtle fluctuations in vascular dynamics [6].

Recent animal experiments integrating fUSI with intracranial recordings have demonstrated that fUSI signals exhibit

strong correlations with neuronal firing rates at frequencies typically below 0.3 Hz [7]. This frequency range, consistent with the slow hemodynamic responses in small-animal models, raises the question of whether fUSI can capture sufficient information to reliably distinguish different brain states in humans, both healthy and pathological.

Epilepsy is characterized by episodes of hyperexcitability leading to seizures. In this context, real-time fUSI could be used to detect rapid changes in the hemodynamic response during pre-ictal or ictal phases [8]. By contrast, Alzheimer’s (AD) is marked by more subtle, long-term disruptions in neuronal communication and potential hyperexcitability in specific regions, partially caused by amyloid-beta and tau pathology [9], [10].

Ultrasound imaging that captures network-wide changes in blood flow might highlight diffuse patterns of dysfunction reflective of AD progression. We hypothesize that the slower dynamics of fUSI, compared to direct electrophysiological measurements, may still retain sufficient information for robust classification—particularly for chronic conditions such as AD. However, for transient phenomena like seizures, performance may be more sensitive to sampling frequency and variability in hemodynamic response.

This work evaluates fUSI-based brain state classification via a computational pipeline. Neural mass models simulated electrophysiological signals, which were converted to fUSI traces using an experimentally derived hemodynamic response function [11], [7]. Pathological conditions (epilepsy, Alzheimer’s) were modeled by adjusting excitation-inhibition parameters. A 1D convolutional neural network then classified healthy vs. pathological states, comparing raw electrophysiological and fUSI signals. This simulation-based approach provides initial insights into the feasibility of fUSI for brain state classification, motivating future validation with experimental data.

II. METHODS

A. Neural Activity via the Wilson-Cowan Model

We employed the Wilson-Cowan (WC) neural mass model to simulate the collective dynamics of local excitatory (E) and

inhibitory (I) populations [11]. The WC model is an established framework that captures emergent population-level behaviors including oscillations, multi-stability, and bifurcations, making it suitable for replicating healthy and pathological states.

The model is governed by:

$$\tau_E \frac{dE(t)}{dt} = -E(t) + S_E \left(w_{EE} E(t) - w_{EI} I(t) + E_{\text{ext}}(t) \right), \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_I \frac{dI(t)}{dt} = -I(t) + S_I \left(w_{IE} E(t) - w_{II} I(t) + I_{\text{ext}}(t) \right), \quad (2)$$

where:

- $E(t)$ and $I(t)$ denote the average firing rates of excitatory and inhibitory populations at time t .
- τ_E and τ_I are the corresponding time constants.
- $w_{EE}, w_{EI}, w_{IE}, w_{II}$ encode the connection strengths between populations.
- $E_{\text{ext}}(t)$ and $I_{\text{ext}}(t)$ represent external input currents (e.g., from neighboring or upstream populations).
- S_E and S_I are sigmoidal activation functions of the form:

$$S_X(x) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[-\alpha_X(x - \theta_X)]}, \quad (3)$$

with α_X and θ_X controlling the steepness and threshold for each population $X \in \{E, I\}$.

Additionally, a stochastic component was included via an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process (intensity $\sigma = 0.1$ and timescale $\tau = 5ms$).

We used the *neurolib* Python library [12] to generate time-series data. For simplicity, a single local node (excitatory-inhibitory pair) was simulated under three conditions: a healthy control (HC) reference, an epilepsy-like state, and an AD-like state.

Control condition: The model parameters for the control condition were chosen in accordance with previous studies on typical Wilson-Cowan dynamics [13], [14]. Specifically, the parameters were set to $w_{EE} = 16$, $w_{EI} = 18$, $w_{IE} = 12$, $w_{II} = 3$, with external inputs $E_{\text{ext}} = 3$ and $I_{\text{ext}} = 0.1$. These values yield stable yet responsive excitatory-inhibitory dynamics.

AD condition: Alzheimer's disease has been associated with both hyperexcitability and diminished inhibitory function [9, 10, 15]. We emulated this by increasing w_{EE} and w_{EI} (enhancing excitatory drive and excitatory-to-inhibitory coupling), while slightly reducing w_{IE} (weakened inhibition). This aligns with evidence that certain cortical circuits in AD show a shift toward excitation: the modified parameters were: $w_{EE} = 16 \times 1.20 = 19.2$, $w_{EI} = 18 \times 1.20 = 21.6$, $w_{IE} = 12 \times 0.80 = 9.6$, and external inputs $E_{\text{ext}} = 3$, $I_{\text{ext}} = 0.1$.

Epilepsy condition: Epilepsy is characterized by hyperexcitable neuronal populations often subject to increased external drive [13]. We mimicked this by boosting E_{ext} and also slightly increasing w_{EE} and w_{EI} : the modified parameters

were $w_{EE} = 19.2$, $w_{EI} = 21.6$, $w_{IE} = 12$, with external inputs $E_{\text{ext}} = 3.6$ and $I_{\text{ext}} = 0.1$. These alterations can lead to large-amplitude oscillations reminiscent of epileptiform activity.

Each condition was simulated for 100 seconds, and 100 independent realizations were generated per condition. The integration step was 0.1 ms, stored at 1 ms intervals to balance computational load and temporal fidelity.

B. Simulated Ultrasound Data

Hemodynamic response function (HRF). To translate electrophysiological (E/I firing rates) signals into fUSI-like signals, we convolved the simulated neural activity with an HRF derived from fUSI measurements in rodent hippocampus [7]. In that study, a regularized regression approach was used to map multi-site neuronal activity onto ultrasound-measured CBV changes. We used the published HRF corresponding to spontaneous hippocampal activity in the absence of external visual stimuli. Mathematically, let $n(t)$ be the neural activity (combined excitatory minus inhibitory activity, or simply excitatory activity) at time t . The fUSI signal $u(t)$ is then:

$$u(t) = (n * h)(t) = \int_{\tau=0}^{\tau=t} n(\tau) h(t - \tau) d\tau, \quad (4)$$

where $h(\cdot)$ is the HRF. In practice, we perform this convolution using the `fftconvolve` function from the Python *scipy* library to ensure computational efficiency. The resultant $u(t)$ was downsampled to match an assumed fUSI sampling rate of 1 Hz, consistent with typical fUSI frame rates for small-animal imaging.

C. Classification Task

We tested whether simulated fUSI data retain enough information for binary classification of brain states. Separate classifiers distinguished control vs. epilepsy and control vs. AD. Each condition had 100 time series, forming a balanced dataset of 200 samples. Additionally, of the original 100 seconds signal only the central 30 seconds were retained to eliminate border effects. Data were split into 70% training, 20% validation, and 10% test sets. A 1D CNN classified electrophysiological or fUSI signals. Each sequence was adjusted to 300 points via zero-padding or subsampling. After a trial and error procedure, the selected CNN featured three convolutional layers (kernel size = 10 for the electrophysiological data and kernel = 100 for the fUSI data to compensate for its lower sampling rate, stride = 10) with 64, 128, and 256 output channels, each followed by ReLU, batch normalization, and dropout. Global average pooling reduced feature maps to a 256-dimensional vector, fed into a fully connected layer with a sigmoid activation for binary classification. The model was trained using Adam (learning rate 10^{-4} , weight decay 10^{-5}) with binary cross-entropy loss for 100 epochs, applying early stopping if validation loss stagnated for 10 epochs. Performance was assessed on the test set using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

III. RESULTS

A. Simulated Ephys and fUSI Traces

Figure 1 showcases the workflow for a representative Control run. The top panel (blue) highlights the raw electrophysiological output (Ephys) from the Wilson-Cowan model (excitatory population). The middle panel illustrates the HRF from [7], averaged over hippocampal recordings. Finally, the bottom panel (red) shows the resulting fUSI signals obtained via convolution of the electrophysiological trace with the HRF.

Fig. 1: Example data generation for the control condition. (Top) Raw excitatory population activity from the Wilson-Cowan model. (Middle) The hemodynamic response function. (Bottom) Simulated fUSI signal: the convolution of the neural activity with the HRF.

Visual inspection reveals that the derived fUSI signal is significantly smoothed and delayed relative to the original electrophysiological trace, reflecting the slower dynamics inherent to hemodynamic coupling.

B. Classification Performance

Table I summarizes the binary classification metrics on the test set for each pathology vs. control comparison. Each comparison was performed on two data types: (1) raw electrophysiological signals and (2) simulated fUSI signals.

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Control vs. AD (Ephys)	95.0%	95.4%	95.0%	94.9%
Control vs. AD (fUSI)	80.0%	80.0%	80.0%	79.9%
Control vs. Epilepsy (Ephys)	95.0%	95.6%	95.0%	95.0%
Control vs. Epilepsy (fUSI)	65.0%	66.2%	65.0%	65.4%

TABLE I: Summary of classification performance for each pathology vs. control.

For the AD comparison, the classification on electrophysiological signals achieved near-perfect performance (95% accuracy, 95.4% precision, 95% recall, 94.9% F1). On simulated fUSI signals, performance remained quite high (80% accuracy, 80% precision, 80% recall, 79.9% F1), suggesting that the slower hemodynamic dynamics still contained enough distinct features to separate AD from healthy patterns.

In contrast, for the epilepsy comparison, the network trivially distinguished raw electrophysiological signals (95%

accuracy, 95.6% precision, 95% recall, 95% F1). However, these metrics lowered on simulated fUSI data (65% accuracy, 66.2% precision, 65% recall, 65.4% F1). This suggests that the transient and potentially faster oscillations characteristic of epileptiform activity are more difficult to capture under the low-frequency constraints of fUSI-like signals.

Figures 2 and 3 show learning curves for AD and epilepsy classification using electrophysiological and fUSI data over 10 and 100 epochs, respectively. For AD, both modalities converge stably, though fUSI shows slightly higher final validation loss. For epilepsy, electrophysiology converges quickly with low loss, while fUSI struggles to find a robust solution.

Fig. 2: Learning curves for AD vs. Control classification (top: ephys, bottom: fUSI).

Fig. 3: Learning curves for Epilepsy vs. Control classification (top: ephys, bottom: fUSI).

IV. DISCUSSION

Our findings suggest that functional ultrasound imaging, despite its slower hemodynamic timescale, can still reveal differences between healthy and certain pathological brain states. For Alzheimer's disease (AD), network dysfunction arising from changes in excitatory-inhibitory balance and reduced effective connectivity [9], [10], [15] produced signals distinguishable even after low-pass filtering. This resulted in 80% accuracy when classifying AD vs. healthy data, implying that stable or slowly evolving pathologies retain enough distinct features for fUSI-based detection.

By contrast, epilepsy involves transient, high-frequency events that may not be fully captured by the slower hemodynamic response. While raw electrophysiological data reliably distinguished epileptic from healthy signals, convolved fUSI traces obscured these rapid changes, leading to lower performances. More sophisticated approaches, including higher frame rates, multi-channel data, or additional physiological signals, may be necessary to enhance fUSI's utility in detecting seizures. Expanding to multi-node or large-scale brain models [13], [16] and adopting region-specific hemodynamic parameters could further improve applicability. Lastly, the learning curves indicate potential overfitting, methods like cross-validation and regularization to improve generalization performance could be used. Nevertheless, fUSI's success with AD underscores its potential for disorders characterized by persistent neurovascular alterations.

V. CONCLUSION

We simulated electrophysiological activity via the Wilson-Cowan model and transformed it into fUSI-like signals using an empirically derived hemodynamic response function. A 1D CNN then classified healthy vs. pathological states. While AD-related changes were readily detectable, epilepsy's rapid dynamics were harder to distinguish in the slower hemodynamic representation, highlighting both the promise and limitations of fUSI. Future efforts should explore larger-scale connectivity models, optimized hemodynamic parameters, and multi-modal strategies to refine fUSI-based detection of diverse neurological conditions.

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